

THE INDIRECT OBJECT (IO) – ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH

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Abstract:

The aim of this study is to incorporate the function of the indirect object between Albanian and English language. The function and the Albanian typical case for indirect object are dative and ablative. This grammatical phenomena is the full contrast between two languages because in English language doesn't exist dative and ablative as in Albanian. In Albanian and English language, the indirect object is more heterogenic than the direct object. The indirect (direct) object in both of languages is the receiver (object) of the action within a sentence. It is typically the noun, all possessive pronouns (in the function of nouns), noun phrase that follows the verb, although the indirect object and subject complements can also occupy this position. The direct and indirect object have some characteristics in common, and this fact justifies their sharing term of object.

Keywords: Indirect Object, similarities, differences, contrasts, generative, Albanian, English, noun, pronoun, noun phrase, case (nominative, dative and ablative), definite and indefinite nouns, article

Introduction

In both of languages, we have two forms of indirect object:

- a. Noun, (noun phrase) or pronoun.
- b. Noun, noun phrase or pronoun **with preposition**.

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The indirect object is the noun or pronoun that receives the direct object. Typically, an indirect object precedes the direct object and can be found by question (kë, Çfarë – **who, whom or what**) received the direct object e.g (Al).

Nënës i shfaqët fyryra e birit.

IO

Me takon **mua** ta them.

IO

I besoj **mësuesit** dhe u be **zemërgurⁱⁱ** .

IO

I besoj **atij**.

IO

I ndihmoj **shokut**.

IO

I ndihoj **atij**.

IO

If you would like, we can give **Atat's** the tickets.

IO

The typical question for indirect object are / kë or çfarë – who, whom or what/ and received the direct object. It is the same in both of languages. In English language, the indirect object can make with noun and pronoun, too e.g. (Eng).

John sent her **mother's** a ticket for the bus.

IO DO

Beni sold a friend his car.

S P IO DOⁱⁱⁱ

John didn't send **his brother**. He sent **a ticket** to her mother. Most grammarians subscribe to no-synonymy rule in language. There is a general assumption among linguists that no true synonyms exist among words or structures. Why then do we have two ways to express recipients in English? While **I threw Signe the ball seems**, on the surface to mean the same thing as **I threw Signe the ball seems** these two sentences are not quite synonymous. Speakers who find **I threw the ball to Signe the ball but she couldn't it** a perfectly acceptable sentence often balk at? **I threw Signe the ball but she couldn't catch it**. A number of grammarians have pointed out that with certain verbs an

ⁱⁱ Shkelqim Millaku, [European Journal of Education Studies](http://www.oapub.org/edu), ISSN: 2501 – 1111; ISSN-L: 2501 - 1111; Available on-line at: www.oapub.org/edu, f.95

ⁱⁱⁱ Shkelqim Millaku, 2016, [The noun phrases](http://Academia.edu), Academia.edu, p.1-14

NP indirect object reflects successful completion of the transfer while an indirect object is silent on the issue.^{iv} In Albanian and English, the indirect object is new information and function than the direct object that is given information or opposite.

Unë **i** dhashë **atij** disa libra.

S P IO DO

I bought them for Teuten.

IO DO

I learnt it **in library**.

IO DO

She sold it **to my sister**.

IO DO

I bought **her** **some flowers**^v.

IO DO

I bought them for Teuten.

IO DO

I learnt it in library.

IO DO

She sold it **to my sister**.

IO DO

I bought **her** **some flowers**.

IO DO

In Albanian and English, there is another type which construction with the proposition. Consider the following sentence.

Ata do të kërkonin **nga të rinjtë** zbatimin më përpikmeri të dëtyrave.

IO

Arat cleaned the car **for Benin**

IO

Hakui hung the picture **for his teacher**.

IO

^{iv} Lynn Berk, 1999, **English Syntax**, London, p. 41.

^v Shkelqim Millaku, 2016, [The contrast of Direct object between Albanian and English Language](http://www.onlinejournal.in) - Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research, ISSN: 2454-1362, <http://www.onlinejournal.in> - <http://www.onlinejournal.in/IJIRV2I7/253.pdf>, Issue-7 of IJIR, p. 1410 -1420.

How we saw by the example the indirect object is the second object in sentence, usually with two objects. In both of languages, normally the indirect object has placed in sentence before the direct object.

The indirect object can realized by the personal pronoun in Albanian and English too e.g.

Agrani ma dha **mua** librin.

IO DO

Teuta gave **me** a book.

IO DO

Teuta gave a book **to me**.

DO IO

In Albanian language is one type with proposition e.g.

Teuta shkoi në mal **me të vëllain**.

IO

It is the same in English language e.g.

Teuta went to mountain **with his brother**.

IO

The function of the indirect object is (saw) associated with the first of two complements, both of which are characterized by their ability to function as subject in a corresponding passive sentence.^{vi}

The local Council has awarded **him** a scholarship.

IO

The University granted **Professor Harvey** leave of absence.

IO

Could you call **me** a taxi?

IO

^{vi} Flor Aarts, 1988, English syntactic structure. Cambridge, p. 239.

The function of the indirect object is normally realized by a noun phrase and only very rarely by a finite /kë, çka, çfarë, ku --- what, where, why, when/-clause etc. The direct object and indirect object are (can be) both structures within the predicate e.g.

The function of indirect object is associated with the first of two complements, both of which are characterized by their ability to function as subject in a corresponding passive sentence:^{vii}

- a. The local Council has awarded **him** a scholarship.
- b. **He** has been awarded a scholarship by the local Council.

The firm offered **Jim** the job.

The firm offered the job **to Jim**.

"Beni sold a friend his car.

S P IO DO

I bought the kids a computer.

S P IO DO''^{viii}

Conclusion

In both of languages the object normally follows the subject and the predicate. The indirect object usually comes before the direct object e.g.

I bought the kids a computer.

S P IO DO''^{ix}

The kids devoured **the liver**.

S P DO

^{vii} Flor Aarts, 1988, English syntax structure. Cambridge, p. 139.

^{viii} Shkelqim Millaku, 2016, THE FUNCTION OF NOUN PHRASES BETWEEN ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH, The 2016 WEI International Academic Conference Proceedings Vienna, Austria, p. 113-120.

^{ix} Shkelqim Millaku, 2016, THE FUNCTION OF NOUN PHRASES BETWEEN ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH, The 2016 WEI International Academic Conference Proceedings Vienna, Austria, p. 113-120.

John gave Hanrry a **book**.

S P IO DO

Most people and scholars would probably regard a subject + verb + direct object sentence as the prototypical English sentence.

The function and the Albanian typical case for indirect object are dative and ablative. This grammatical contrast between two languages are presented and studied in this paper. In Albanian and English language, the indirect object is more heterogenic than the direct object. The indirect (direct) object in both of languages is the receiver (object) of the action within a sentence. It is typically the noun; all possessive pronouns (in the function of nouns), noun phrase and all of them follow the verb.

References

1. Bauer, Laurie. **English Word-Formation**, London, 1983.
2. Celce-Murcia, Mariana. **The Grammar book**, USA, 1999.
3. Celce-Murcia, Marianne. **The Grammar book**, USA, Heinlein, 1999.
4. Chomsky, Noam. **Syntactic Structure**, New York, 2002.
5. Christopher Pountain, M.F.Lang, **Spanish Word Formation**, London, 1990.
6. Doyle, Arthur Conan. **The lost world and other thrilling tales**, London, 2001.
7. Eddings, David. **Magician's Gambit**, London, 1983.
8. **Fjalor i Gjuhës se Sotme Shqipe**, Tiranë, 1980.
9. **Fjalor i Termave të Gjuhësisë**, Tiranë, 1975ë botuar nga Akademia e Shkencës e RPSH-Instituti i Gjuhësisë dhe i letërsisë, sektori i terminologjisë.
10. **Fjalori i shqipes së sotme**, Tiranë, 2002.
11. Germizaj, Shukrane. **A comprehensive handbook of English Grammar**, Prishtine, 2004.
12. **Gramatika e Gjuhës shqipe I**, Tiranë, 2002.
13. Grup autorësh, **Fjalor i fjalëve të huaja**, Prishtinë, 1988, f.315.
14. Henderickson, Robert. **Word and phrase origins**, New York, 1997.
15. Jokli, Norbert. **Naim be Frashëri e pasunimi i gjuhës shqipe**, Gjurmime albanologjike, seria shkencore filologjike II, 1972, Prishtinë, 1974.
16. Kabashi, Jashar. **English Grammar Morphology**, Prishtine, 2000.
17. Kadare, Ismail. **Përbindëshi**, Tiranë, 2005.
18. Kostallari, A. **Mbi disa veçori të fjalës së përbërë në gjuhë shqipeë** Studime mbi leksikun dhe mbi formimin e fjalëve në gjuhën shqipe I, Tiranë 1972.

19. Liz and John Soars, **New Headway Advanced, Student's book**, Oxford, 2003.
20. Master, Peter. **English grammar and technical writing**, Washington, 2004.
21. Millaku, Sh. (2009). **Kontributi i Zellik Harris për gjuhësinë**, IASH. Tetovë.
22. Millaku, Sh. (2015). **Kërkime gjuhësore**. Prizren.
23. Millaku, Sh. (2011). **Studime gjuhësore I**. Prishtinë.
24. Millaku, Sh. (2011). **Strukturat sintaksore**. Prishtinë.
25. Millaku, Sh. (2009). (Profesor Selman Riza dhe Albanologjia) **Studimet e Selman Rizes në fushën e morfologjisë**. Korçë, f. 143-150.
26. Millaku, Sh. (2011). **Historiku i nyjës se prapme (kontrast me gjuhët ballkanike)**, Edukologjia, nr.2, f.81-96. Prishtinë.
27. Newmark, Leonard; Philip Hubbard, Peter Prifti, **Standard Albanian**, California, 1982.
28. Qesku, Pavli. **Fjalor Anglisht-Shqip, English-Albanian Dictionary**, Tiranë, 2002.
29. Quirk, Randolph; Sidney Greenbaum, **University Grammar of English**, London, 1973.
30. Shakespeare, William. **Measure for Measure**, London, 1995.
31. Shakespeare, William. **Measure for Measure**, London, 199t.
32. Shakespeare, William. **Richard III**, Denmark, 1993.
33. Shakespeare, William. **The Winter's Tale**, Denmark, 1995.
34. Thomaj, Jani. **Leksikologjia e gjuhës shqipe**, Tiranë, 1974.
35. Veljko Gortan, Oton Gorski, Pavao Paush, **Gramatika latine**, Prishtinë, 1985.
36. Xhuvani, Aleksande. **"Kompozitat", Studime mbi leksikun dhe mbi formimin e fjalëve në gjuhën shqipe I**, Tiranë 1972.
37. Yule, George. **Oxford practice grammar**, Oxford, 2008.
38. Shkelqim Millaku, [The contrast of Direct Object between Albanian and English language](http://www.onlinejournal.in), ISSN: 2454-1362, [http://www.onlinejournal.in](http://www.onlinejournal.in/IJIRV2I7/253.pdf) - <http://www.onlinejournal.in/IJIRV2I7/253.pdf>
Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research, Dubai, 2016.
39. Shkelqim Millaku, The contrast of the gender between Albanian and English language, International Journal of Thales Educational Sciences (THEDS) ISSN (print): 2149-5130 - http://media.wix.com/ugd/d4d001_2582d04ef0264786b60ca6e76227ebc3.pdf 1-15; Vol.2, No.1, Turqi, 2016
40. Shkelqim Millaku, 2015, The Compound Nouns, https://www.academia.edu/6091482/The_Compound_Nouns
41. Shkelqim Millaku, 2016, [The Noun Phrases](http://www.anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/viewFile/580/647), Anglisticum Journal, <http://www.anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/viewFile/580/647>

42. Shkelqim Millaku, 2015, [The Direct Object](http://anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/233), Anglisticum Journal, <http://anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/233>, Retrieved on February 17, 2016.
43. Shkelqim Millaku, 2015, [The Genitive](http://www.anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/156), Anglisticum Journal, <http://www.anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/156> Retrieved on February 17, 2016.

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